

Jewellery History Today

Issue 46 · Winter 2023
ISSN 2042-8529

The magazine of The Society of Jewellery Historians

Images of Jewellery on Neolithic Stelae from the 3rd Millennium BC

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Over 1,300 anthropomorphic stelae have been found in Europe and to date these are the earliest known large-format sculptures. Stone stelae reached their greatest distribution in the 4th and 3rd millennia BC in regions ranging from the Atlantic to the Caucasus, and these vary in height from half to twice the size of a human being. It took hundreds of hours to make and erect such sculptures; this was only possible through joint communal effort. The people who made them lived in the Neolithic period, a time of economic and technological innovations. Their lives were shaped by animal power, domestic animal husbandry, livestock farming, new metallurgical skills, mobility and the opening up of new territories. This seems to have been accompanied by a new self-image. The stelae are likely to have been created as ancestral images and depict individuals, whilst embodying the values and traditions of a group, and their collective memory.

The sculptures are characterised by geometric forms and focus on the essentials. Faces are rudimentary, consisting of a prominent nose and eyes or eyebrows, while the mouth is often omitted. Body parts such as arms, or even legs and feet, are engraved on the body or depicted in relief to complete the human form. They are also adorned with weapons, jewellery and clothing.

Jewellery and weapons found in contemporaneous graves prove the attributes represented on the stelae existed and are accurately depicted. The 2021 exhibition *Humans – Carved in Stone*, at the Swiss National Museum, Zurich, provided a unique opportunity to study about 40 stelae from various countries side by side and additional artefacts from this period gave us further insights. The focus here will be on the jewellery seen worn on a female stele named Arco 4 (the 'Lady of Arco'), from Etschtal in Trentino-Alto Adige dating back to the first half of the 3rd millennium BC (fig. 1) found together with other female and male sculptures. Arco 4 is characterised by an oval face with a prominent eye area and nose, while breasts identify the figure as female. Two ribbons bound across the forehead with rectangular patterns are thought to represent a diadem

Fig. 1. Female stele, Arco 4 (the 'Lady of Arco') from Etschtal in Trentino-Alto Adige, Italy, wearing a diadem with pendants and prominent pectoral ornament. Marble, H.: 86 cm. Museo Alto Garda, Riva del Garda. Photograph: © Archivio Museo Alto Garda, Gardaphoto.

or other type of headdress. Attached to this on either side of the face are two disc-like pendants with concentric circles. Rows of curved grooves from face to waist cover her upper body and breasts ending with a border of dots. This breast ornament shapes her silhouette.

Multi-strand necklaces are commonly found on anthropomorphic stelae, particularly from the Languedoc-Rouergat region in Southern France. A prominent example is that of the 'Lady of Saint-Sernin' wearing a six-strand necklace above the breasts, a Y-shaped pendant and belt (see cover). Although some traits are intrinsic to particular regions, there are similarities in the manner the bodies, jewellery and weapons are depicted. This suggests Neolithic communities were closely interconnected.

The necklace on Arco 4 covering the chest area is not an isolated example; other female stelae in the region (Arco 3, Arco 5, Arco 7 and Algund 1) feature

identical pectoral ornaments. Finds in contemporaneous local graves give clues regarding the materials used for jewellery. Thousands of beads found in collective burials at the Necropolis of Manerba del Garda vary both in form (disc- or cross-shaped, tubular) and material (stone, shell, bone, animal teeth and copper). In the grave of a woman buried in the late 3rd millennium BC at La Vela di Valbusa near Trento, a breast ornament was found which was created from shells and bones in varying shapes. Thus, the breast ornament depicted on Arco 4 may have consisted of numerous strands of beads.

Men's costumes from Trentino-Alto Adige, like Arco 1, feature such necklaces, but as a single-strand (fig. 2). Male stelae are shown armed to the teeth: Arco 1 sports a valuable dagger below the necklace and weapons such as halberds and axes. Above the elaborate garland-shaped belt typical of the region are six more daggers with their tips pointing towards the abdomen.

The jewellery depicted proves the inhabitants of Trentino-Alto Adige had close contact with their neighbours in nearby valleys. In fact, the jewellery worn by the 'Lady of Arco', like the breast ornament and diadem with pendants, was also prevalent in Valcamonica and Valtellina in the 3rd millennium BC (fig. 3). In comparison to other stone stelae the examples here rarely show a human silhouette. Such figurative compositions are closely related to rock art as found engraved on immobile boulders. The human form is often indicated by the arrangement of motifs and sometimes by an elaborated shoulder. Interestingly, many of these sculptures are multiphase; they have been reworked several times, which means that even depictions of men and women could alternate on the same stone. This was detected on the stele from Latsch in Vinschgau and on a stele from Vezzano in Trentino-Alto Adige (Vezzano 2).

The Italian researcher Stefania Casini has studied motifs found on stelae from Valcamonica and Valtellina in Lombardy extensively. On female

Fig. 2. Male stele Arco 1 from Etschtal in Trentino-Alto Adige, Italy, shown wearing weapons, a necklace and a garland-shaped belt. Limestone, H.: 215 cm. Museo Alto Garda, Riva del Garda. Photograph: © Archivio Museo Alto Garda, Gardaphoto.

depictions she interprets a striking U-shaped motif as a multi-strand necklace or a type of shawl. The stele Caven 3 found in Teglio (fig. 3) wears a jewellery ensemble similar to that of the 'Lady of Arco'. Above, in a central position, the circle engraved with concentric lines represents a diadem from which three decorative ribbons are suspended. The circular motifs on either side are pendants, like those seen on the 'Lady of Arco'. The large U-shaped motif below could be a necklace or breast ornament. The lower rim is decorated with a serrated border, while on the 'Lady of Arco' it is a dotted border. These ornamental motifs appear in varying combinations in Valcamonica and Valtellina, which may suggest they are indicators of the social status of the wearer. An example of this are the two additional double-spiral pendants on Caven 3, which can be found on stelae from Sion and the Aosta Valley as well as original pendants made of copper in various collections. These motifs spread over the stone's surface depict complex female costumes and how they changed over time.

Men's costumes also relate to those of Arco. Circular motifs in the upper part of stelae from Valcamonica and Valtellina were originally believed to symbolise the sun; more recent research has interpreted these as single-strand necklaces. As these motifs appear in combination with weapons, these are assumed to represent male individuals. The necklaces could either be made of beads or animal teeth as previously mentioned (fig. 2).

Whilst men wore necklaces, the ladies of Arco were adorned with prestigious pectoral ornaments. Their material composition remains unknown, and despite grave finds pointing to strands of beads, fabric with appliqué beads cannot be excluded. Finally, we are reminded of the Mold gold cape from Wales in the British Museum, London, dating from 1900-1600 BC in sheet-gold embossed to mimic strings of beads (fig. 4). Like the 'Lady of Arco', the Mold cape held the wearer's arms close to the body. The cape is probably ceremonial and is reminiscent of the pectoral ornaments seen on the stelae of the Neolithic Age.

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Fig. 3. Female stele Caven 3 from Teglio in Lombardy, Italy wearing an ensemble of jewellery: diadem with pendants and ribbons, U-shaped necklace and two double-spiral pendants. Tonalite, H.: 80 cm. Museo archeologico di Palazzo Besta, Teglio. Photograph by kind permission of the Ministero della Cultura-Direzione Regionale Musei Lombardia.

Fig. 4. The 'Mold Cape', sheet gold, c. 1900 BC - 1600 BC, H.: 23.5 cm. Museum no: 1836,0902.1. © British Museum.